

Economic Evaluations of Implementation Strategies in Health and Social Care Settings: a Scoping Review Protocol

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Abstract

Introduction: Despite the rapid growth of implementation science, economic evaluations of implementation strategies remain rare, with fewer than 10% of studies including comparative economic analyses. Previous reviews have pointed out the scarcity of economic evaluations and the lack of consistent methodologies when it comes to evaluating the costs of implementation as well as health and implementation outcomes. This scoping review aims to identify and compare economic evaluations of implementation strategies adopted in health and social care settings and assess their methodological quality.

Inclusion criteria: This review will focus on economic evaluations of implementation strategies adopted in health and social care settings, including all types of populations for which an evidence-based intervention and implementation strategies are being tested. Results may be presented in ICER format, depending on the type of economic analysis, or include at least cost together with health outcomes and/or implementation outcomes. Eligible sources include, but are not limited to, hybrid effectiveness-implementation studies, RCTs, clinical trials, pragmatic trials, non-randomized trials, multicentre studies, and simulation (modelling) studies, as long as they clearly state the use of implementation strategies, published since 2000.

Methods: This scoping review will follow the Joanna Briggs Institute methodology searching in MEDLINE, Embase, Econlit, and PsycINFO. Two independent reviewers will screen studies against inclusion criteria and one reviewer will extract data on economic evaluation methods, and assess study quality using tools like CHEERS or ECOBIAS. Data will be extracted from papers included in the scoping review using Covidence's data extraction tool. Findings will be presented in tabular format, highlighting key concepts and methodologies.

Keywords

Cost-effectiveness; health economics; implementation science; ICER

Introduction

Despite the remarkable growth of implementation science over the past two decades and the extensive number of successful studies evaluating the effectiveness and implementation outcomes of interventions and implementation strategies (1,2), economic evaluations of intervention implementation remain largely unexplored (3,4). Fewer than 10% of implementation studies aimed at improving clinical practice guidelines report details on implementation costs. Even fewer include economic evaluations, such as cost-effectiveness analyses of implementation strategies (4,5). The available literature presents available information heterogeneously, preventing effective comparisons of the cost and effectiveness of strategies employed in these studies (4).

Implementation strategies are a critical component of implementation projects, designed to facilitate the long-term adoption of evidence-based interventions by healthcare practitioners (6). The economic implications of implementation strategies must be clear to ensure that funders, policymakers, and decision-makers recognize the effects and costs of applying these strategies and are able to make informed decisions (4).

Economic evaluations in healthcare involve systematic assessments of the costs and outcomes of healthcare interventions, programs, or policies. These evaluations aim to determine the most efficient use of resources by comparing alternative options in terms of both their financial costs and health benefits. Examples of economic evaluations in healthcare include cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA), cost-utility analysis (CUA), cost-benefit analysis (CBA), and cost-minimization analysis (CMA) (7). Budget impact analysis (BIA) specifically evaluates the affordability and financial feasibility of adopting an intervention, considering the financial implications from the perspective of healthcare payers, governments, or institutions. It helps assess whether the intervention can be implemented within existing budgets without jeopardizing other essential services (8).

Economic evaluations of implementation strategies are crucial for decision-making within resource-constrained health systems, as they help identify strategies that maximize intervention uptake at the lowest possible cost (9). These analyses involve explicit comparisons of different approaches to introduce positive changes in healthcare, evaluating the costs associated with developing, executing, and participating in implementation activities in relation to the achieved effects (3,4). However, despite the increasing healthcare costs and the critical need for effective resource allocation, decisions about which implementation strategies to choose are often not guided by economic evaluations due to a lack of evidence (4,10).

In the early 2000s, two reviews examined the use of economic evaluations in assessing the implementation of evidence-based guidelines (11,12). The authors concluded that the available evidence on the cost-effectiveness of implementation strategies was limited in both quality and scope. Subsequent reviews have largely focused on the costs of various implementation strategies without fully considering their effectiveness (13,14). In further reviews the authors have delved into specific contexts, such as low- and middle-income countries (15), while others have concentrated on particular areas of health and social care, including public health (16), clinical settings (17), or specific types of implementation strategies, such as those aimed at guideline adoption (5). Additionally, one review has looked at a very specific setting and type of strategy namely implementation guidelines on low back pain management in primary care (18).

To our knowledge, the most comprehensive work in this area that had a look at economic evaluations of implementation strategies is a systematic review by Roberts et al. (19), which examined the progress made in incorporating economic evaluations into implementation science, specifically regarding the quantity and quality of health-economic evidence published in this field since the early 2000s. While there have been advancements in economic evaluations within implementation science, there is still, to our knowledge, no established methodology to systematically account for the resources allocated to implementation strategies (20). Since Roberts et al.'s literature search was done in 2016, nearly a decade has passed, highlighting the need for a new, up-to-date review of the literature that expands the synthesis of evidence. We want to find out what methodologies are used to carry out economic evaluations of implementation strategies to appreciate the state of the literature. Therefore, the objective of this scoping review is to identify and methodologically evaluate economic evaluations of implementation strategies in health and social care settings.

In addition to the exploratory search in MEDLINE via Pubmed we searched Zenodo and the Center of Open Science (OSF) and no published or underway systematic reviews or scoping reviews on this topic were identified.

Review questions

1. What types of economic evaluations of implementation strategies are used in health and social care settings?
2. How are these economic evaluations performed in terms of data collection (i.e., what type of data are collected and how – retrospective or prospective)?
3. How is the methodological quality of economic evaluations of implementation strategies in health and social care settings?

Eligibility Criteria

The following eligibility criteria will be applied to select studies for inclusion in this review. An overview of the criteria, along with a list of reference papers, is provided in table format in [Appendix A](#).

Participants

The scoping review will encompass all types of populations for which an evidence-based intervention and implementation strategies are being tested. Individuals receiving treatment or care, as well as those employed within the designated settings, will be included.

Concept

We will include studies with any type of evidence-based interventions where implementation strategies are applied. Studies in which implementation strategies are not employed, will be excluded from the present review.

Context

All studies conducted within health and social care settings (e.g., hospitals, long-term care facilities, home care, schools, social services) will be included.

Outcomes

We will include studies that report results as Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER), depending on the type of economic analysis, or include at least cost together with health and/or implementation outcomes. Studies that only provide cost data, without evaluating health or implementation outcomes, will be excluded.

Types of sources

Eligible sources for the scoping review include, but are not limited to, hybrid effectiveness-implementation studies, RCTs, clinical trials, pragmatic trials, non-randomized trials, multicentre studies, and simulation (modelling) studies. Study protocols, reviews, meta-analyses, editorials, and opinion papers will be excluded. Studies published in any language will be considered for inclusion. However, if the language of the publication is not understood by any of the researchers involved in the scoping review, or cannot be automatically translated, the study will be excluded. Only studies published from the year 2000 onward will be included, as this will encompass the literature following the inclusion of the MeSH term 'Implementation Science'.

Methods

A junior researcher (SH) together with the INTERSCALE research team will conduct a scoping review following the methodological framework for scoping reviews in accordance with the Joanna Briggs Institute methodology for scoping reviews (21).

Search Strategy

A preliminary search in MEDLINE via PubMed was conducted to identify articles on the topic. The words used in the title, abstract, and keywords of the seed publications will inform the development of the search strategy for databases including MEDLINE via PubMed, Embase, Econlit and psycINFO, in order to identify literature on economic evaluations of implementation strategies. The search strategy, including all identified keywords and index terms, will be adapted for each included database. The reference list of all included sources of evidence will be screened for additional studies. In an early step in the development of the search string, the search strategy will be discussed with a scientific librarian (medical information specialist). The search strategy will be developed iteratively in collaboration with the research team, incorporating relevant keywords and Subject Headings terms related to economic evaluations and implementation science.

Evidence selection

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and duplicates removed. Titles and abstracts will then be screened by two independent junior reviewers (SH, IP) for assessment against the inclusion criteria for the review. Potentially relevant sources will be retrieved in full and their citation details imported into Covidence, which will be the online tool used to streamline the review process. The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by two independent reviewers (SH, IP). Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, and a third person, a senior researcher (JB), will be consulted for final decision making. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR) flow diagram (22).

Data extraction

Data will be extracted from papers included in the scoping review by an independent junior reviewer using Covidence's data extraction tool.

Data extraction will involve collecting information on study characteristics, the intervention and implementation strategies used, key findings about costs and effectiveness and will focus on the methods used in the study to do the economic evaluations. We will differentiate the methods used by assigning them to one of the main types of economic evaluations used in health economics:

- cost-benefit analyses
- cost-utility analyses
- cost-effectiveness analyses
- cost-minimization analyses
- cost-consequence analyses
- budget impact analysis

A draft extraction form is provided in [Appendix B](#). The draft data extraction tool will be modified and revised as necessary during the process of extracting data from each included evidence source. Modifications will be detailed in the scoping review. If appropriate, authors of papers will be contacted to request missing or additional data, where required.

The methodological quality of the included studies will be assessed using the CHEERS checklist (23) and additionally using the ECOBIAS checklist (24) for model-based economic evaluations.

Data analysis and presentation

We will explore the occurrence of key concepts in the included literature, including the use of ICER, defined perspective and time horizon, types of data gathered, populations studied, types of intervention and implementation strategies used and other relevant elements of the economic analyses. This exploration will help us assess the quality of the studies included in the review, providing a clearer understanding of the methodologies and findings within the field. We will present our findings in tabular format.

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Conflicts of interest

The proposed scoping review is not subject to any conflicts of interest.

Dissemination

This literature review will be submitted to a scientific journal once completed.

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Appendix A – Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria, and Reference Papers

	Include	Exclude
Participants	People treated/cared for or working in the selected settings	-
Concept	All types of evidence-based interventions where implementation strategies are applied	Studies in which implementation strategies are not employed
Context	Health and care settings (hospitals, long-term care facilities, home care, schools, social services etc.)	-
Outcomes	Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER) or must include at least cost together with health and/or implementation outcomes	Studies that only provide cost data, without evaluating health or implementation outcomes
Types of sources	Hybrid effectiveness-implementation studies, RCTs, cRCTs, non-randomized trials, clinical trials, pragmatic trails, evaluation studies, multicenter studies, simulation studies (modelling studies)	Study protocols, reviews, meta-analyses, editorials, opinion papers
Other	From year 2000 onwards	-

Seed papers

Olmstead TA, Yonkers KA, Forray A, Zimbrea P, Gilstad-Hayden K, Martino S. Cost and cost-effectiveness of three strategies for implementing motivational interviewing for substance misuse on medical inpatient units. *Drug Alcohol Depend.* 2020 Sep 1;214:108156.

Bartakova J, Zúñiga F, Guerbaai RA, Basinska K, Brunkert T, Simon M, et al. Health economic evaluation of a nurse-led care model from the nursing home perspective focusing on residents' hospitalisations. *BMC Geriatr.* 2022 Jun 9;22(1):496.

Yanguela J, Pence BW, Udedi M, Banda JC, Kulisewa K, Zimba CC, et al. Implementation strategies to build mental health-care capacity in Malawi: a health-economic evaluation. *Lancet Glob Health.* 2024 Apr;12(4):e662–71.

Hartzler B, Hinde J, Lang S, Correia N, Yermash J, Yap K, et al. Virtual Training Is More Cost-Effective Than In-Person Training for Preparing Staff to Implement Contingency Management. *J Technol Behav Sci.* 2022 Oct 12;1–10.

Eiraldi R, Lawson GM, Glick HA, Khanna MS, Beidas R, Fishman J, et al. Implementation fidelity, student outcomes, and cost-effectiveness of train-the-trainer strategies for Masters-level therapists in urban schools: results from a cluster randomized trial. *Implement Sci.* 2024 Jan 25;19(1):4.

Raghavan R, Fitzsimmons-Craft EE, Welch RR, Jo B, Proctor EK, Wilson GT, et al. Cost-effectiveness of train-the-trainer versus expert consultation training models for implementing interpersonal psychotherapy in college mental health settings: evidence from a national cluster randomized trial. *Implement Sci.* 2024 Jul 29;19(1):55.

Appendix B - Data Extraction Tool

Study details

Unique study ID (i.e. doi)

Reference / citation

Contact author name

Contact author institution

Contact author email / physical address

Publication type

Country study was conducted in

Study setting/s

Trial registration number

Trial registry

Trial start date

Trial end date

Sponsorship / funding source (if any)

Other

Methods

Study aim / objective

Practical relevance for decision making in policy and practice

Study design/type of cost analysis

Setting (Cultural, historical and/or social context)

Health economic analysis plan (reference)

Perspective and reason (e.g., general public, insurance, etc.)

Total study duration

Time horizon (when, how long and why)

Discount rate (what, how much and why)

Intervention (what)

Control (what)

Unit of allocation/analysis (by individuals, cluster/ groups)

Method of randomisation

Prospective / Retrospective / Cross sectional

Parallel or Cross-over

Method of recruitment

Timepoints

Blinding (Single, double, triple, no blinding)

If blinded, detail who was blinded (Participant, researcher, outcome assessor, someone else)

Other

Population

Population description (e.g. care home, what type)

Total sample size

Inclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria

Method of recruitment of participants

Clusters (if applicable)

Population - Withdrawals

Intervention

Control

Number of withdrawals/exclusions

Reason for withdrawals/exclusions

Timing of withdrawals/exclusions

Reason of withdrawals/exclusions

Population - Characteristics

Intervention

Control

Sex

Mean age (years) \pm SD

Ethnicity

Other relevant characteristic

Group differences at baseline

Other

Intervention (repeat for each intervention component)

Number of participants allocated

Dose

Frequency

Mode / route of administration

Duration of exposure

Duration of follow-up

Other

Comparator

Number of participants allocated

Dose

Frequency

Mode / route of administration

Duration of exposure

Duration of follow-up

Other

Implementation Strategy. (repeat for each strategy)

Action

Actor

Context

Target

Time (When)

Quantity (How much)

Duration (How long)

Frequency (How often)

Other

Effectiveness Outcome

Type of outcome considered	Measurement unit/valuation	How was measurement done?
e.g. hospitalizations	e.g. QALY	e.g. questionnaire, EQ-5D-5L

Cost Outcome

Type of outcome considered	Measurement unit/valuation	How was measurement done?
e.g. implementation costs	e.g. US \$	e.g. routinely collected

ICER

In which unit is it expressed?

In which quadrant is it?

Economical aspects (from CHEERS guideline)

Currency, price date, and conversion	Report the dates of the estimated resource quantities and unit costs, plus the currency and year of conversion
Rationale and description of model	If modelling is used, describe in detail and why used. Report if the model is publicly available and where it can be accessed.

Analytics and assumptions

Report all analytic inputs (e.g., values, ranges, references) including uncertainty or distributional assumptions.

Characterizing heterogeneity

Describe any methods used for estimating how the results of the study vary for subgroups.

Characterizing distributional effects

Describe how impacts are distributed across different individuals or adjustments made to reflect priority populations.

Stakeholder involvement

Describe any approaches to engage patients or service recipients, the general public, communities, or stakeholders (such as clinicians or payers) in the design of the study.

Effect of uncertainty

Describe how uncertainty about analytic judgments, inputs, or projections affect findings. Report the effect of choice of discount rate and time horizon, if applicable.

Effect of engagement with patients and others affected by the study

Report on any difference patient/service recipient, general public, community, or stakeholder involvement made to the approach or findings of the study

Limitations, generalizability

Report limitations, ethical or equity considerations not captured, and how these could impact patients, policy, or practice